

Immunity augmenting food supplements for susceptible individuals in combating pandemic COVID-19 (Review)

Sangita Agarwal^{1,§}, Srimoyee Saha^{2,◇}, Tathagata Deb^{1,Ξ} and Soumendra Darbar^{3,4,¥}

¹Department of Applied Science, RCC Institute of Information Technology, Canal South Road, Beliaghata, Kolkata-700015, India.

²Department of Life Science and Biotechnology, Jadavpur University, 188, Raja S C Mallick Road, Kolkata-700032, India.

³Faculty Council of Science, Jadavpur University, 188, Raja S C Mallick Road, Kolkata-700032, India.

⁴Research and Development Division, Dey's Medical Stores (Mfg.) Ltd., 62, Bondel Road, Ballygunge, Kolkata-700019, India.

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Abstract

The outbreak of Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) has affected humanity at large all over the globe. The cause of severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) is very much similar to its homologous virus SARS-CoV which caused SARS in many people in 2003. This epidemic started in Wuhan, China and it quickly spread its wings all over the world. COVID-19 has lower severity and mortality than SARS but is much more transmissible and affects more elderly individuals than youths and more men than women. Co-occurrence of distinct ailments like diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular and respiratory issues place individuals at a greater risk of having COVID-19 complications. There is age specific corona spread pattern as observed in cases reported from China and Italy, it is known fact that the general immunity reduces, as one gets older. The health and immunity is mainly determined by what kind of diet we follow, a well-balanced diet containing antioxidants, minerals and vitamins plays a key role in health-promoting, disease-fighting activities of our body. To boost immunity in vulnerable population it is essential to include food and nutritional supplements, which can help in prevention and management of viral infections. This article attempts to provide a timely and comprehensive review of the role of immunity enhanced with balanced diet and nutritional supplements to fight corona virus especially in vulnerable population. During these testing times when no conclusive medication is available strengthening the immune system can also safeguard us from mutating forms of other viruses in the near future too.

Keywords: Coronavirus disease (COVID-19), Immunity, Nutritional Supplements, Vitamins, Macro & Micro elements.

§ Email: mailsangvee@gmail.com

◇ Email: srimoyee10@yahoo.co.in

Ξ Email: Tathagata.chem@gmail.com

¥ Email: darbarsoumendra@gmail.com, Head of the Department, Research and Development Division, Dey's Medical Stores (Mfg.) Ltd., 62, Bondel Road, Ballygunge, Kolkata-700019 Contact No.: 9477153353, (Corresponding Author).

1. Introduction

The world is experiencing a severe survival challenge as novel Coronavirus disease has turned out to be a psychophysical and social crisis of unparalleled magnitude. Like all other viruses, Coronavirus (CoV) is also dependent on cell machinery of host for its survival and yet it more than 200 countries have been effected by this deadly virus [1-4]. The transmission potential of any disease is its reproductive number measures it and it dies out naturally when its value is less than one [5]. During the 1918-influenza pandemic, the reproductive number was 1.8, which resulted in 50 million casualties, effecting one third of world population at that time [6]. It has been reported that overall rate of mortality per confirmed COVID-19 cases is nearly 4.5 percent but the actual reproductive number might be higher because of some undetected cases [7]. The severity and recovery rate of the disease is dependent on the age and health of the subjects. The younger age group without any pre-health condition is expected to have a low death rate (0.2 percent) whereas older population (above 80) have much higher death rate (15 present) [8]. Till date no direct or indirect medication is available presently that can fight against Covid-19. Only supportive care is the only solution for saving lives of those affected by these deadly invisible microbes. Scientists and medical professionals throughout the globe are engaged to find out its remedy which can save lives.

Fig. 1. Corona virus infections, recoveries and deaths, worldwide.

Source data: Worldometer. URL: <http://www.worldometers.info/>

2. Microbiology and Pathogenicity of Corona Viruses

Coronaviruses have a single stranded RNA genome, covered by an enveloped structure. It is either pleomorphic or spherical in shape encapsulated by glycoproteins on its surface (diameter 80-120 nm). Unlike the other RNA viruses, the RNA genome of CoV is one of the largest. Its genetic material is susceptible to frequent recombination process, which can give rise to new strains with alteration in virulence [9, 10]. The structural protein of this RNA virus consists of Spike Protein (S), envelope protein (E), membrane protein (M), and nucleocapsid phosphoprotein. These proteins mediates virus entry and is a primary determinant of cell tropism and pathogenesis [11, 12].

3. Immunopathology of COVID-19

The pathogenesis of COVID-19 is still under investigation and site of initial infection of SARS-CoV-2 is unknown. Since COVID-19 is a respiratory disease it might affect only lungs as the symptoms include fever, cough, sore throat, shortness of breath, loss of smell and or taste and pneumonia in some cases [7]

Man to man transmission especially through close contact is the major cause of infection in COVID-19 patients. A small droplet from the nose or mouth of a person with COVID-19 can affect millions together in contact [13, 14]. The unaffected person becomes prone to this disease by personal contact or by contact through contaminated surfaces including paper, cardboard, steel, glass, wood, etc. The incubation period of corona virus which is probably between 2-14 days is crucial because during this time it can be transmitted [15-17]. Few of COVID-19 hospitalized patients developed lymphopenia, pneumonia and additionally, in extremes cases high-levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines were observed. These findings are consistent with the pathogenesis of SARS and MERS, so we can hypothesize similarly that presence of lymphopenia and “cytokine storm” have major role to play in COVID-19. This can initiate viral sepsis and inflammatory-induced lung injury leading to other complications including pneumonitis, respiratory failure, and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), organ failure and potentially death [18-20].

Figure 2. Effects of COVID-19 on respiratory system leading to other complications.

Source: Corona virus image. URL: <https://elemental.medium.com/what-the-coronavirus-image-youve-seen-a-million-times-really-shows-3d8de7e3eb1f>

Some authors have reported decreasing values of haemoglobin and neutrophil counts in most COVID-19 infected patients. When the patients' hemoglobin decreases than the body accumulates too many harmful iron ions, which causes inflammation in the body and this also leads to increase in C-reactive protein and albumin. Hemoglobin, the oxygen carrier, is a protein and is made up of four polypeptide chains (α_1 , α_2 , β_1 , and β_2) and each polypeptide chain is attached to a heme group which consists of porphyrin linked to an iron atom. These iron-porphyrin complexes coordinate oxygen molecules reversibly, an ability directly related to the role of hemoglobin in oxygen transport in the blood. When iron is in Ferrous state (II), haemoglobin captures oxygen in alveolar cells and releases carbon dioxide, thereby oxidizing iron to Ferric state (III). The process is reversed when hemoglobin reaches other cells in

the body through the blood. Thus, it is interpreted by the clinical findings that the proteins of viral machinery target hemoglobin, causing the heme to dissociate into iron and porphyrin, thus capturing porphyrin. Both the lungs and hemoglobin play major role in exchanging carbon dioxide and oxygen. Corona virus attack on hemoglobin would yield iron, carbon dioxide, and oxygen, which might put both lung cells in a toxic and inflammatory state [21-24].

Many countries all over the world have announced lockdown to control the community transmission but humanity cannot sustain under lockdown forever, it is just a precautionary measure but not a solution. This can help in minimizing the spread of infection but without any cure till date how can individuals protect themselves?

The protective mechanism lies within us, which is our immune system. Immunity is our body's defense mechanism against attack by any invading microorganism or pathogens. It can be less specific and more specific type of response directed to a particular pathogenic microbes. It is also helpful in eliminating toxic or allergenic substances that enter through our mucosal surfaces. These immune responses at times may or may not have long lasting memory. It is a known fact that a person recovering from small pox is most unlikely to suffer from it again as he has acquired specific immunity [25, 26].

4. Nutritional supplements and immunity

There is lack of acquired immunity in populations across the world against Covid-19. No anti-viral medications are available in the market there is also an uncertainty about the true infection rate within countries. Mostly the elderly constitute the vulnerable group and are confined in homecare system. The general principle is to eat a balanced diet containing seasonal fruits and green vegetables as well as taking nutritional supplements as advised by nutritionist. Specific advice in relation to the elderly is to increase the intake of Vitamin E (134mg-800mg/day), Zinc (30mg-220mg/day), Vitamin C (200mg-2g/day), Vitamin D (10µg-100 µg/day), particularly those having less serum Vitamin D level [27]. These nutritional supplements enhance T cell and B cell (antibody) in humans including the elderly. It does make pragmatic sense to support our immune system to make it healthy so as to fight Covid-19 before, during and after infection [28].

5. Food supplements

Good nutritive food is vital not only during any infection but also after it. Infected body becomes weakened especially when these cause fever, to regain the strength the body needs extra energy and nutrients [29]. Therein lies the importance of balanced and healthy diet not only in any type of infection but more so in these times where the whole world is affected by this pandemic.

While no food or dietary supplements can cure COVID-19 infection, but our immune system can only sustain itself on the diet, so a strong immune system would require a well balance diet [30].

This pandemic has caused anxiety and stress to all beings and this result in turn into sleep disturbances, so it's a vicious cycle as stress and sleep disturbances are complementary to each other. In order to get good sleep it has been advised that people should consume food containing or promoting the synthesis of serotonin and melatonin at dinner. The diet should be inclusive of varieties of plant species along with roots, leaves, fruits, and seeds like almonds, bananas, cherries, and oats which contain melatonin and/or serotonin or tryptophan. Milk and milk products are the main sources of tryptophan, which is the sleep-inducing amino acid. It is also involved in the regulation of satiety and caloric intake via serotonin that mainly lowers carbohydrate and fat intake, and thereby inhibiting neuropeptide Y which is the most powerful hypothalamic orexigen peptide [31, 32]. Proper protein supplements especially plant and sea food proteins are mandatory during Covid-19 infection for children, adult and elderly people. Proper sufficient protein provides essential amino acids which fight against virus. Apart from this both macro and micro elements rich diet are recommended to build the body's immunity. Regular intake of leafy vegetables also provides vitamins and mineral supplement.

Antioxidants like beta carotene, vitamin C and vitamin E, contain micronutrients and they increase the number of T-cell subsets and also enhance lymphocyte response to mitogen, correspondingly augments interleukin-2 production. The main sources of beta Carotene are sweet potatoes, carrots, and green leafy vegetables while vitamins C is found in red peppers, oranges, strawberries, broccoli, mangoes, lemons, and other fruits and vegetables. Nuts, seeds, spinach, broccoli and vegetable oils (soybean, sunflower, corn, wheat germ, and walnut) are rich in vitamin E [33]. Several studies have reported that fruits and vegetables supplying micronutrients can boost immune function.

6. Existing COVID-19 Care

Currently no specific treatment for COVID-19 as with many other viruses throughout the globe. People are tested for COVID-19 based on the symptoms but some COVID-19 patients are asymptomatic too. The testing kits are very important in assessing the rates and pattern of the virus. A person tested positive for COVID-19 is

hospitalized and isolated to avoid further transmission to others. In the existing scenario because this deadly virus has high rate of transmission people not testing positive for COVID-19, should still maintain social distancing [34].

Persons having mild COVID-19, having flu-like symptoms, are not hospitalised and treated symptoms at home. They are isolated from others including family members. This includes separate sleeping and eating arrangements etc. Indisputably, a person having nutritional deficiency would have impaired immune functions, thereby inadequate in protecting us against disease or potentially-damaging foreign bodies. Consequently, we should understand the importance of maintaining a healthy immune system which is crucial at all times especially so during the COVID-19 outbreak. Moreover, our lifestyle which includes excess alcohol consumption, smoking and similar bad habits and other factors like poor diet and malnutrition, stress, lack of sleep weaken immunity [35]. However, vitamins can play a vital role in optimizing immune functions by boosting the body's defense mechanism and resistance to infection.

7. Role of Vitamin C and Zinc in Reducing Risk of Coronavirus

Vitamin C and zinc are known to be immunity² boosting nutrients. Their intake can increase body's ability to fight against pathogens and protect from infection. There are various ways in which vitamin C helps our immune system. Firstly, it promotes growth of lymphocytes that are white blood cells containing antibodies. These immune cells attack foreign substances that invade our body to protect us. Secondly, vitamin C has been found to improve the activity of phagocytes, which are immune cells capable of swallowing harmful pathogens. Thirdly, they have anti-oxidant properties that help in reducing and preventing inflammation which is a known factor behind a weak immune function. Zinc is an essential micro-nutrient, which helps in cell growth and its survival. Zn acts as a messenger for immune system. It functions as an intra-cellular signal molecule for

² URL: <https://www.india.com/lifestyle/diabetes-these-food-can-boost-your-immunity-and-keep-you-healthy-than-before-3883951/>

body's defense cells. It also reduces level of cytokines, chemicals that are harmful for body [36]. Zn also helps in boosting production of WBC and T cells which wards off infection. It has been reported that Zn inhibited severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) coronavirus RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp) template binding and elongation in Vero-E6.

8. Food supplements that increase Body's immunity

Red bell peppers reign supreme when it comes to fruits and vegetables high in vitamin C. According to the U.S.³ research one cup of chopped red bell peppers (211%) contains twice the amount of vitamin C that is found in an orange (106%). Vitamin C can lower risk of respiratory infections and also improve immune function. It helps in the growth and repair of tissues⁴ in our body. Broccoli is packed with phytochemicals⁵, vitamin C and vitamin E, it supports our immune system and can help protect cells from damage caused by free radicals as well as fight off bacteria and viruses. Strawberries are also good source of 50% of daily required vitamin C. Spinach is rich in vitamin C, beta carotene and vitamin A. Chickpeas contain a lot of proteins, an essential macromolecule made of amino acids that help in growth and repair of the body's tissues. It is also involved in synthesizing and maintaining enzymes to keep our systems functioning properly. Chickpeas are also packed with zinc, which helps in controlling the immune system and regulating immune responses. Garlic contains high concentration of Sulphur containing compounds which is linked to its health benefits such as immunity boosting abilities, lowering of blood pressure and reducing risk of heart disease. Mushrooms contain high amount of vitamin D which can help enhance the absorption of calcium, which is good for bone health, and may also protect against some cancers and respiratory diseases⁶ [37].

³ URL: <https://fdc.nal.usda.gov/fdc-app.html#/food-details/170108/nutrients>

⁴ URL: <https://www.eatright.org/food/vitamins-and-supplements/types-of-vitamins-and-nutrients/how-vitamin-c-supports-a-healthy-immune-system>

⁵ URL: <https://www.aicr.org/resources/blog/healthtalk-whats-the-difference-between-an-antioxidant-and-a-phytochemical/>

⁶ URL: <https://www.bmj.com/content/356/bmj.i6583>

Figure 3. Common immune boosting food ingredients those fight against COVID-19 infection.

Source: URL: <https://utswmed.org/medblog/easy-immune-boosting-food-covid19> and compiled.

Recent⁷ studies⁸ have focused on the effectiveness of probiotics in fighting the common cold and influenza-like respiratory infections. Yogurt is a great source of probiotics that facilitate a healthy gut and immune system. Sunflower seeds have high content of vitamin E, which works as an antioxidant and helps to boost the immune system. One ounce of dry-roasted sunflower seeds

gives 49% of our daily need of vitamin E, according to the NIH⁹, Table (1).

As discussed earlier, the haemoglobin levels decrease in patients having COVID-19 infection so if we can augment the haemoglobin levels we can help in recovery of such patients. Certain food sources like Pomegranates, dates, beetroots, legumes, pumpkin seeds and watermelons and others sources is given in Table (2) can help in increasing hemoglobin levels.

⁷ URL: <https://www.karger.com/Article/FullText/496426>

⁸ URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5995450/>

⁹ URL: <https://ods.od.nih.gov/factsheets/VitaminE-HealthProfessional/>

Table 1: COVID-19: Immune System Boosters.

Sl. No.	FOOD SUPPLEMENTS	SOURCES	DAILY INTAKE	UPPER LIMIT
1.	Zinc	lean meats, seafood, milk, whole grains, beans, seeds, and nuts	M: 11 mg, W: 8 mg	40 mg
2.	Vitamin-C	broccoli, cantaloupe, kale, oranges, strawberries, tomatoes, guava, and lychee	M: 90 mg, W: 75 mg Smokers: Add 35 mg	2,000 mg
3.	Vitamin-E	Nuts, seeds, wheat germ, green leafy vegetables, avocado, and shrimp	M: 15 mg, W: 15 mg (15 mg equals about 22 IU from natural sources of vitamin E and 33 IU from synthetic vitamin E)	1,000 mg (nearly 1,500 IU natural vitamin E; 2,200 IU synthetic)
4.	Vitamin-D	Oily fish, egg yolk, veal and mushrooms	31–70: 15 mcg (600 IU) 71+: 20 mcg (800 IU)	50 mcg (2,000 IU)
5.	Vitamin-A	Sweet potatoes, carrots, red bell pepper, spinach, black-eye peas, and mango	M: 900 mcg (3,000 IU) W: 700 mcg (2,333 IU) Some supplements report vitamin A in international units (IU's).	3,000 mcg (about 10,000 IU)
6.	Vitamin-B6	Green vegetables, chickpeas, and cold-water fish such as tuna or salmon	31–50 years old: M: 1.3 mg, W: 1.3 mg; 51+ years old: M: 1.7 mg, W: 1.5 mg	100 mg
7.	Iron	Lentils, spinach, tofu, and white beans	19–50: M: 8 mg, W: 18 mg 51+: M: 8 mg, W: 8 mg	45 mg
8.	Selenium	Organ meats, seafood, walnuts, sometimes plants (depends on soil content), grain products	M: 55 mcg, W: 55 mcg	400 mcg
9.	Calcium	Yogurt, cheese, milk, tofu, sardines, salmon, fortified juices, leafy green vegetables, such as broccoli and kale (but not spinach or Swiss chard, which have binders that lessen absorption)	31–50: M: 1,000 mg, W: 1,000 mg 51-70: M: 1,000 mg, W: 1,200 mg, 71+: M: 1,200 mg, W: 1,200 mg	2,500 mg
10.	Potassium	Meat, milk, fruits, vegetables, grains, legumes	M: 4.7 g, W: 4.7 g	10 mg
11.	Manganese	Fish, nuts, legumes, whole grains, tea	M: 2.3 mg, W: 1.8 mg	11 mg
12.	Magnesium	Green vegetables such as spinach and broccoli, legumes, cashews, sunflower seeds and other seeds, halibut, whole-wheat bread, milk	M: 2.3 mg, W: 1.8 mg	11 mg
13.	Phosphorus	Wide variety of foods, including milk and dairy products, meat, fish, poultry, eggs, liver, green peas, broccoli, potatoes, almonds	M: 700 mg, W: 700 mg	31–70: 4,000 mg 71+: 3,000 mg

Note: M = Men; W = Women. **Source:** URL: https://www.onhealth.com/content/1/immune_system_boosting_foods and compiled.

Table 2: Essential food supplements which increase haemoglobin levels.

Sl. No.	Food supplements	Sources
1.	Vitamin C rich diet	Oranges, lemon, bell peppers, tomatoes, grapefruits, berries
2.	Iron rich food	Green leafy vegetables, liver, tofu, spinach, eggs, whole grains, pulses and beans, meat, fish, dry fruits
3.	Folic acid reach food	Green leafy vegetables, sprouts, dried beans, peanuts, bananas, broccoli, liver

Source: URL: <https://www.ndtv.com/food/9-foods-that-can-help-increase-haemoglobin-1828770> and compiled.

9. Conclusion

Scientists, medical professionals and researchers are working round the clock all over the world in pioneering a medication and/ or a vaccine, and possible medication strategy, for this pandemic, until then our immune systems will need to adapt to fight COVID-19 unaided. A strong immune system will work as our multi-level defence network against potentially harmful bacteria, viruses and other pathogens which we touch, ingest and inhale every day. A healthy lifestyle helps one's immune system to be in the best shape possible to tackle pathogens, but prevention is always better than cure. The coronavirus pandemic has turned the world's attention to our immune system and people now are trying to understand about their own strengths and weaknesses. At this juncture the only ray of hope seems to overcome the weakness of immune system by boosting it. So, in this pandemic situation healthy food supplements containing protein, vitamins, macro and micro elements can only help us to fight against the viruses especially older people and boosts body's immune power.

Our immune system works in synchronized manner in responding to the threats of the environment. Since conception, the baby is protected by mother's immune system, before his immunity develops and later we start neglecting our immune system as we grow old. We need to apply our understanding of the fundamentals of immunology to reinforce and repurpose the immune response, providing us with power to protect us against infection.

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Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

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